

1. Introduction

The teacher, as nobody else, has to know how to relax not for days, weeks or months, but for a couple of minutes. The main element of the pedagogue's internal technique is the regulation of his emotional sphere, formation of the emotional stability in his professional work [1, p. 12]. That's why the research of the peculiarities of the intending teachers' self-regulation skills formation is relevant for theory and practice.

In the scientific works we meet different definitions of the notion of "self-regulation". It consists of two parts: "regulation" (lat. regulare – to keep order, to normalize) and "self" (shows that the element of the regulation is inside the system) [2].

Scientists consider self-regulation as the psychical activeness process of a person concerning initiation, setting up, administration, supporting with different types and forms of activeness, personal purposes [3, p. 10].

Self-regulation is administration of psycho-emotional state, that is achieved by means of the person's self-influence with words, imagine shapes, managing of muscles and breathing [4, p. 114]. Self-regulation is managing of worries, feelings, imagination, attention. It includes the skills of changing physical state, keeping in anger, irritation, resentment; stimulation of calmness, working mood, demonstration of confidence, benevolence and optimism [5, p. 32]. Self-regulation is demonstrated with the ability to show self-confidence, energy, mobility and activeness. It is achieved in the way of the person's influence on herself. The pedagogue's self-regulation is the person's integrative property that includes her intellectual, motivational, willy, emotional spheres. It may promote conscious, purposeful and effective doing of the professional actions on the base of valuable motives, finding of the optimal and harmonic way of activity [6, p. 189].

Judging from practice, more attention at pedagogical universities is paid to the preparation of students to teaching rather than to self-regulation. Lately this problem wasn't the object for special researches. As a result, pedagogues' self-regulation depends on the circumstances what influences badly on the educational process.

Aim: to find out the present level of self-regulation skills of intending teachers as a result of using traditional and innovation methods of self-regulation in their professional preparation.

INTENDING TEACHERS' SELF-REGULATION SKILLS FORMATION

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Abstract: The main element of the pedagogue's internal technique is the regulation of his emotional sphere. Self-regulation is the process of controlling of the psycho-emotional condition, feelings, imagination and attention. It is shown in the ability to look self-confident, energetic, active, and is achieved in the way of influence of the person on herself. Practically, self-regulation of pedagogues depends on the circumstances what influences badly on the educational process.

77 students of the fourth year of study took part in this research. With the help of the questionnaire, the effectiveness of the influence of different types of self-regulation was determined. On the base of the findings, the motivational, the cognitive and the active self-regulation criteria were defined. On their base the students were divided into three groups according to the level of the development of self-regulation: high, medium and low.

Most of the students belong to the group of the medium level of self-regulation according to the three criteria. Speaking about the motivational and the active criteria, on the low level there are more intending teachers rather than on the high level. Though, according to the cognitive criterion, the high level was shown in more cases than the low one.

Most students understand that it is possible to influence on one's emotional state but they don't know how to do it quickly. The intending teachers have low developed skills of self-regulation as they don't have the experience of using them and haven't chosen the most appropriate method for them yet. They suffer from emotional instability, feel high tension in unpredictable or conflict situations, can't control their emotions. Besides, the students are eager to control their emotional state, know theoretically how to do it, but don't have enough practice to strengthen the knowledge.

Keywords: formation, self-regulation, methods, control, skills, emotions, criteria, levels, students, intending teachers.

Task: to determine the sense of the notion "self-regulation", criteria and levels of self-regulation skills; to check the present level of this skill of the intending teachers.

3. Methods

77 students of the fourth year of studying in the department of physical education and sport in Vinnytsia Mykhailo Kotsiubynskyi State Pedagogical University took part in the empirical research.

By means of the questionnaire the effectivity of the influence on the psycho-emotional sphere of different methods of self-regulation was determined. In order to process the results, the methods of quantitative and qualitative analysis, in particular regressive analysis, were used. The received data was considered as variables in the multiplane analysis. The linear regression gives a possibility to analyze the individual influence of each variable (in our research – the method of self-regulation) on the final result (psycho-emotional state of intending teachers). By means of questionnaire, observation and expert assessment, the level of self-regulation skills of intending teachers was determined.

4. Research

In order to decide the effectivity of the self-regulation methods' influence on the psycho-emotional sphere, the reaction of the intending teachers on using such methods was analyzed. (The questionnaire "The style of self-regulation of behavior" [7]). The results are shown on Fig. 1.

Fig. 1. Level characteristic of correlation between knowledge about self-regulation and its using in everyday life

Comparing the data, we can affirm, that the most popular therapy among the intending teachers is the music therapy

(35.0 %), but only 13.3 % of them know, that while listening to music, it is possible to change ones' emotional state [8, p. 123]. 29.3 % of students know, that massage helps to decrease stress, but only 13.4 % use it. Unfortunately, the smallest amount of students like reading books (3.3 %), though 3.9 % know about their curable properties. The reasons for such difference are the absence of knowledge about the methods of self-regulation, low level of motivation and disability of controlling an emotional state.

Students have learned how to use two types of influence on emotions. The first one: changing of mimic, pantomimic, tension of muscles, tempo and depth of breathing, movements, steps. The second one: managing of imagination, self-management. Managing the imagine shape, students tried to influence their thoughts, mood, wishes, needs [5, p. 37].

The analysis of the correlation of the knowledge about the methods of self-regulation and their usage in everyday life by intending teachers gives a possibility to define three criteria of self-regulation of the intending teachers: motivational, cognitive and active.

Motivational criterion of intending teachers' self-regulation skills is shown in their attitude towards their own emotional state, in their orientation for self-management methods realization. The indexes of the motivational criterion are:

- the interest in self-regulation; need of self-regulation skills formation;
- feeling of pleasure after using of the self-regulation methods;
- the system of orientations which make the intending teachers to regulate themselves;
- a wish to work on the own emotional state;
- aspiration for self-analysis.

The indexes of the **cognitive criterion** are:

- a complex of knowledge in general pedagogical disciplines: pedagogics, the basic course of pedagogical technique, psychology, physiology;
- the system of knowledge about the basics of professional self-regulation, rules of psychical functions and development of an organism, criteria of the emotional state and the methods of emotional self-improving diagnosis;
- knowledge about their emotional state, peculiarities of the character, strong and weak sides;
- knowledge about the sense, aims, ways, directions and organization-methodological basics of the self-regulation skills formation; knowing of the terminology in this field.

The indexes of the **active criterion** are:

- the ability to evaluate the personal emotional state, using different diagnostic methods;
- activity while self-regulation;
- ability to plan, organize and provide self-regulation;
- knowing about different methods, and techniques of the self-regulation;
- ability to choose the optimal self-regulation techniques;
- ability to show or to keep in one's emotions;
- ability to control the personal behavior;
- ability to analyze consequences, positive changes in self-regulation.

The analysis of the self-regulation criteria permits to speak about three levels of the self-regulation skills formation for the intending teachers: high, medium and low.

In this case, the **high level** may be characterized with:

- the presence of stable interest towards the problem, the methods and techniques of self-regulation;

- aspiration for improving;
- high level of theoretical and practical knowledge and abilities that can be used practically;
- realization of every possibility for independent and artistic work;
- having enough will, initiative, responsibility, self-reliance.

The **medium level** has such peculiarities:

- presence of interest and positive attitude towards the problem;
- the system of knowledge is big enough, though the system of self-regulation abilities and skills is formed insufficiently;
- using of some self-regulation methods is episodic, what in its turn doesn't give enough level of the behavior coordination;
- low level of activeness and self-confidence;
- the appearing obstacles become serious barriers. Help, stimulation or a piece of advice is needed;
- some will strains, positive motivation for self-regulation are expressed poorly.

We can speak about the **low level** of the self-regulation formation when the person:

- is indifferent, uninterested and even attitudes negatively towards self-regulation;
- has no wish to test herself, her abilities;
- has no wish to improve herself in this sphere;
- has poorly-expressed motivation;
- always needs stimulation and persuasion of other people when self-regulation is needed;
- can't independently come to a determination about the improvement of emotional state.

Usually such students have depression.

On the basis of the worked up criteria the level of self-regulation skills formation of the intending teachers was found out. It is shown in **Table 1**.

Table 1

The levels of self-regulation skills formation of the intending teachers according to the criteria, %

Criteria of self-regulation	Level of self-regulation		
	Low	Medium	High
Motivational	31.6	43.0	25.4
Cognitive	19.2	58.9	21.9
Active	27.4	55.7	16.9
Average value	26.0	52.5	21.4

Judging from **Table 1** we see, that the biggest amount of students is on the medium level of self-regulation skills formation according to the three criteria. The motivational and the active criteria are on the low level in case of most students, rather than on the high level.

4. Discussion

Most students understand that it is possible to influence on one's emotional state, but they don't know how to do it quickly. To our mind, the students have low-developed self-regulation skills, as they don't have the experience of using different means of it and choosing the most appropriate one for them. The intending teachers suffer often from emotional instability, feel

tension in unpredictable and conflict situations, can't control their emotional state; they know theoretically how to do it, but don't know how to use the knowledge, as they don't have enough practice.

The given data is confirmed by the results of other researchers, who studied motivational peculiarities of academic self-regulation of students, including studying the correlation of its different levels [9, p. 589]; types of independent-dependent self-regulation of a teenager taking into consideration psychological mechanism of his development [10, p. 47], given in **Table 2**.

Data of the **Table 2** shows, that the medium level of students' self-regulation is in priority in the researches of all the scientists. The lowest indexes are on the high level.

Table 2
Indexes of dividing of the students' self-regulation levels in researches of different scientists

Comparison		Levels of self-regulation		
Authors	N, %	Low	Medium	High
Hubina S. I.	N=77	21	40	16
	%	26.0	52.5	21.4
Yatsiuk M. V.	N=440	130	293	16
	%	29.5	66.6	3.6
Kuznetsov O. I., Fomenko K. I.	N=44	18.2	40.3	19.7

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